

THE USE OF SYNTACTICAL STYLISTIC DEVICES IN POETRY

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Abstract: this article compares different syntactical stylistic devices used in poems by several poets in order to show the importance of the syntactical stylistic devices in literature.

Key words: sentence, syntactical level, ellipsis, asyndeton, parallelism, inversion

Introduction. A sentence, as a specific linguistic unit, is a series of somewhat autonomous lexical and phrase units (words or combinations of words). What sets a sentence apart from a word is its mutable structure; it doesn't have a fixed length and can be shortened, extended, complete, incomplete, simple, compound, or complex. Furthermore, its components, length, word order, and communicative type (assertion, negation, question, exhortation) can vary¹. When stylistically analyzing a sentence at the syntactic level, it's acknowledged that the most prevalent and currently used are two-part sentences that contain a subject and predicate, and possibly some secondary elements, with a standard word order and function.

Stylistic study of the syntax begins with the study of the length and the structure of a sentence but is not reduced to it. Such things as word order, communicative function and punctuation are also to be considered. The effect of the majority of other syntactical stylistic devices depends on either the

¹ M.A.K. Halliday & Robin P. Fawcett (eds.), *New developments in Systemic Linguistics*. London: Frances Pinter. 64-93

completeness or quantitative characteristics of the structure or on the arrangement of its members (V.A. Kukharenko², Y.M. Skrebnev³).

Literature review. According to I. Galperin⁴, stylistic devices are a conscious and intentional literary use of language elements, including expressive means. These devices elevate the most crucial structural and semantic features of language forms to a generalized level, thereby creating a generative model. Most stylistic devices are seen as enhancing the emotional or logical emphasis in the corresponding expressive means.

Stylistics is traditionally regarded as a field of study where the methods of selecting and implementing linguistic, extra-linguistic or artistic expressive means and devices in the process of communication are studied (Mistrík, 1985)⁵. In general, we distinguish linguistic stylistics and literary (poetic) stylistics. The division between the two is by no means easy or clear. In his book “Exploring the Language of Poems, Plays and Prose” by Mick Short comments on this problem like this: “... stylistics can sometimes look like either linguistics or literary criticism, depending upon where you are standing when looking at it. So, some of my literary critical colleagues sometimes accuse me of being an unfeeling linguist, saying that my analyses of poems, say, are too analytical, being too full of linguistic jargon and leaving insufficient room for personal preference on the part of the reader. My linguist colleagues, on the other hand, sometimes say that I am no linguist at all, but a critic in disguise, who cannot make his descriptions of language precise enough to count as real linguistics. They think that I leave too much to intuition and that I am not analytical enough. I think I have got the mix just right, of course!”⁶

Data and analysis. Syntactic expressive means and stylistic devices of the English language:

² Кухаренко В.А. (1971) Seminars in Style, Moscow.

³ Скребнев Ю.М. (1994), Основы стилистики английского языка. М. «Высшая школа».

⁴ Galperin I, “Stylistics”, Moscow, “High School”, (1977)

⁵ MISTRÍK, Jozef (1997): Štylistika. 3. vyd. Bratislava: Slovenské pedagogické naklada-ťel'stvo. 600 s.

⁶ Leech G, Short M, “Style in Fiction” Longman, (1991)

- Reduction of the original sentence model involves techniques like ellipsis, aposiopesis, nominative sentences, and asyndeton.
- Extension of the original sentence model involves methods like repetition, enumeration, tautology, polysyndeton, “it is (was) he, who...”, the emphatic verb “to do”, and parenthetical sentences.
- Changes in word order can be achieved through inversion and detachment.
- Interaction of syntactic structures in context can be seen in parallel constructions.
- Transposition of meaning and connection of constituent parts can be seen in rhetorical questions and parceling.

An elliptical sentence is a syntactic structure that lacks a subject, a predicate, or both. The key components of elliptical sentences are intentionally left out by the speaker when they're semantically unnecessary. In the realm of poetry, this omission of words, which doesn't hinder the reader's comprehension of the expression, is also practiced. For instance, Shakespeare often uses the phrase “I will away” in his plays, where the absent verb is understood to be “go”. Similarly, T.S. Eliot uses ellipsis in a passage from “Preludes⁷”.

*You curled the papers from your hair,
Or clasped the yellow soles of
In the palms of both soiled hands.*

In the second and third lines, the possessive “your” is omitted. However, it's inferred that the woman being addressed by the speaker is holding her own feet's soles with her hands⁸.

Ellipsis conserves the speaker's energy, saves time, and minimizes speech redundancy. It can also expose emotions such as excitement, impatience, and joy in the speaker. As a stylistic tool, ellipsis effectively characterizes protagonists.

In “Dream Variations⁹”, Langston Hughes employs ellipsis to suggest a dreamlike fading away, a rhythmic pause that allows the reader to visualize the dream being described.

⁷ Eliot T.S., “Preludes”, 1917

⁸ <https://www.poetryfoundation.org>

Rest at pale evening . . .

A tall, slim tree . . .

Night coming tenderly Black like me.

A nominative sentence is a type of one-member structure that lacks both a subject and a predicate. It's termed as nominative or nominal because its principal component is a noun or a noun-like element (such as a gerund or numeral). For instance: "Morning. April. Problems". A series of nominative sentences contributes to a vibrant portrayal of events. Collections of nominative sentences are employed to vividly illustrate the timing, location, surrounding conditions, and participants of an action.

Similar to ellipsis, aposiopesis is manifested through an incomplete sentence structure. However, this incompleteness differs in its structural and semantic nature: it occurs when the speaker chooses not to continue and abruptly halts their narration:

*Your bags were packed
and left at the door, the vase you
filled with shells, wrapped in tissue,
your books boxed. I have the whelk.*

In standard syndetic writing, the highlighted sections would contain conjunctions. However, in Blas Falconer's poem "Dear friend¹⁰", the lines gain from asyndeton, which eases and seamlessly integrates the depicted images in a tranquil voice. Asyndeton is versatile, finding applications in daily talk, literature, and popular culture. It can suggest a sense of being overwhelmed or a gradual fading, or it can mirror a specific mood depending on the content of the piece. At times, minimalism is more impactful, and asyndeton demonstrates this in the context of conjunction usage.

⁹ Hughes Langston, "Dream Variations," The Collected Poems of Langston Hughes, the Estate of Langston Hughes, (1994)

¹⁰ Thirty Years of Poetry: a magazine of verse: INDEX TO VOLUMES 1 - 60 October 1912 - September (1942)

The stylistic repetition of language units (individual words, word combinations, or sentences) is a common and powerful stylistic tool. Repetition is the act of repeating words or phrases in a literary work. It's frequently used in poetry or songs to establish rhythm and highlight an idea. Repetition is also commonly used in speech as a rhetorical device to draw attention to an idea. For instance:

*The woods are lovely dark and deep
But I have promises to keep
And miles to go before I sleep,
And miles to go before I sleep.*

These well-known lines are from Frost's "Stopping by the Woods on a Snowy Evening"¹¹. In this scene, the individual is standing in the snowy evening with his horse, admiring the surrounding beauty when his horse alerts him. He's prepared to return because he has worldly duties and tasks to perform. Through repetition, the poet aims to express his dedication to his responsibilities and also imparts rhythm to the lines.

Parallelism is a stylistic device of producing two or more syntactic structures according to the same syntactic pattern:

*We real cool. We
Left school. We
Lurk late. We
Strike straight. We
Sing sin. We
Thin gin. We
Jazz June. We
Die soon.*

The parallel structures in Gwendolyn Brooks' poem "We real cool"¹² lend it a rhythmic and melodic quality. Each parallel sentence adheres to a basic pattern,

¹¹ Frost Robert, "Stopping by the woods in the snowy evening", (1923)

¹² Gwendolyn Brooks, "We Real Cool" from Selected Poems. Copyright (1993)

beginning with pronouns and concluding with nouns and adverbs, except for the first line, which ends with an adjective. Syntactic parallelism is multifunctional. It establishes rhythm, a characteristic of poetry. It renders speech compelling, a trait of publicistic and oratory styles. It highlights crucial information and is commonly used in everyday speech. Parallel structure enhances fluency in writing and improves readability, as it employs word patterns that readers can easily follow and connect. It lends sophistication to language, particularly in writing and advertising. It also brings consistency to professional writing, providing rhythm and balance that guide readers to the precise idea, without any confusion. Furthermore, parallel structures synchronize, repeat, and emphasize the words and ideas of the writers. There are two types of parallelism: partial and complete¹³. In the case of partial parallelism, parallel constructions are to be found within a single sentence as its clauses, e.g. “*It was his custom, to make the report, regard the relations he had seen and the news he had heard*”. In cases of complete parallelism, identical structure is found throughout a number of sentences, e.g. “*He thought it must be a horrible illusion. He thought he was going mad*”.

Inversion is the syntactic phenomenon of intentional changing word order of the initial sentence model:

*Sometime too hot the eye of heaven shines,
And often is his gold complexion dimmed,
And every fair from fair sometime declines,
By chance, or nature's changing course untrimmed:
So long as men can breathe, or eyes can see,
So long lives this, and this gives life to thee.*

In “Sonnet 18¹⁴”, William Shakespeare employs numerous instances of inversion, including anastrophe and anaclysis, in his plays and poetry. In this

¹³ Verdonk, P. (2002), “Stylistics”, Oxford University Press.

¹⁴ Shakespeare William. Shakespeare's Sonnets: Never Before Imprinted. London: Thomas Thorpe. (1609)

renowned sonnet, Shakespeare rearranges the word order to lend the lines a more poetic and stylized feel. This is evident in the first line of the excerpt, “Sometime too hot the eye of heaven shines.” If arranged in a syntactically correct order, the line would read, “Sometimes the eye of heaven shines too hot.” By concluding the line with “shines,” Shakespeare can create a rhyme with “declines.” The line also emphasizes the parallel between “too hot” and “shines.” There’s also an inversion in the poem’s final couplet with the unusual phrasing, “So long lives this.” This results in a pleasing repetition at the start of the couplet’s two lines with “so long” and an antimetabole of “lives this” with “this gives life.”

Conclusion. The study of stylistics extends beyond the aesthetic appreciation of literary texts. It invites us to delve deeper into the power of language and its potential for meaning-making. The various syntactical stylistic devices discussed serve as a testament to the richness and complexity of language, demonstrating how their effective use can significantly elevate the quality of a text. Stylistics has played a crucial role in the critical linguistic study of the mass media. It has equipped students with the tools to peel back the stylistic practices that often conceal the illegitimate exercise of power, fostering a more critical and informed consumption of media.

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